

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Establishment of an undergraduate examination committee system, working under the Excel 2013 and Visual Basic environment

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Abstract

We will employ the capabilities of the Excel program and our simple experience in the work of the examination committee over the past years to prepare the examination committee system for undergraduate and programming it to serve the interest of the work of the examination committee in our college in particular and in our university in general.

The system prepares for the undergraduate exams committee, and users of the system enter information about the student's performance in the exams with all its details. There are several buttons in the system to implement different commands according to the exam committee's needs.

The outputs of the system will be all the information requested by the committee, which reduces time and effort and is of high accuracy.

Keywords: Committee; Examination; Undergraduate; Excel; System

1. Introduction

Educational systems in information societies have been concerned with preparing individuals to prepare them for good use of computer and information technology to successfully overcome the computer and information gap in the future. The current era is characterized by rapid change, continuous cognitive explosion, social development, and education by nature and conditions based on constant change and continuous development for the better to suit the changes of the age. The change in education is more necessary and urgent because of rapid scientific and technological progress.

The success of any organization, regardless of its activity, is measured first by the ability of management to use the available resources to achieve the goals with great efficiency and great mastery. This can only be achieved by following the latest management methods to accomplish the tasks and the work. Therefore, it is necessary to rely on information technology in university administration. It includes several aspects, including the software systems [1].

The computer management instruction (CMI) does not mean the use of computers in teaching or learning, but what it means is the management of the educational process within the university, where teaching remains a teacher's task, and the management of the educational process by computer aims mainly to improve the educational process and increase its effectiveness, And this requires dealing with a large amount of data, some of them related to students and others related to the staff in the field of teaching and management, statistics and examinations, which can help the computer to address them accurately and quickly [2].

Therefore, the manager must be aware of the prospects of educational development and the future of educational and technological, which are the most important of the development of the performance of school administration and

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education using information technology, because technological development in the educational field is not a luxury or a change in shape or appearance, but is an inevitable response and interaction necessary with the information and technology age [3].

2. Microsoft office excel

Excel is an incredibly powerful tool for getting meaning out of vast amounts of data. However, it also works really well for simple calculations and tracking almost any kind of information. The key for unlocking all that potential is the grid of cells. Cells can contain numbers, text, or formulas. You put data in your cells and group them in rows and columns. That allows you to add up your data, sort and filter it, put it in tables, and build great-looking charts [4].

3. Proposed system

3.1. The system consists of several sheets:

Start with the home sheet, as we can see from figure (1), we can deal with the system by choosing any of the buttons in front of us, and once you click on the button, the relevant sheet will be activated.

Figure 1 Home screen

As we see in figure (2) we enter the basic general information for each university and each college and details of the subjects...etc.

Home	units	subjects
	3	Civil Law (Obligations)
	3	Administrative Law
	3	General Penal Code
	2	Personal Status Law
	2	Public Finance
	2	Political systems
	2	Arabic
	2	Ruling verses
	2	Criminal jurisprudence
	1	Administrative Law (in E
	(Ctrl) ▾	
	College of Law	college name
	second class	class
	2012-2013	study year

Figure 2 Basic information

The following sheet shows the details of the first trail, which includes the student's name, the names of the study subjects and their units, details of the grade of the yearly quest, the grade of the final exam, and all required calculations, as shown in figure (3).

I	subject	Civil Law (Obligations)	Administra tive Law		General Penal Code			Personal Status Law			Public Finance			Political systems			Arabic			Ruling verses			Criminal jurisprude nce			Administrative Law (in English)			sum
		3	3		3			2			2			2			2			2			1						
	full name	annual degree	final exam	final degree	annual degree	final exam	final degree	annual degree	final exam	final degree	annual degree	final exam	final degree	annual degree	final exam	final degree	annual degree	final exam	final degree	annual degree	final exam	final degree	annual degree	final exam	final degree	annual degree	final exam	final degree	
1	Ibtisam Darsh Aliwi Mozan																											1450	
2	Ahmed Alsharif Karim Abdul Razzaq Kazem																												1496
3	Sincerity Qasim Hashem Matar																												1413
4	Areej Rana Alawi Hamid																												
5	Zia Murad Mirza Bowers																												
6	Muhammad Jabr Jasiri bracelets																												
7	Israa Jabbar Sharhan Jahr																												1530
8	Israa Hossain Hadi Taha																												
9	Israa Sobeh Tariq Abbas																												
10	Israa Mustafa Abdel Razzaq																												

Figure 3 First trail details

There are other sheets for the details of the second and supplementary attempt. A paper for printing the certificate, which includes all the information of the student, and it may be for the three attempts as shown in figure (4)

Ibtisam Darsh Aliwi Mozan					
Ministry of higher education and scientific research Al_Iraqia University - Baghdad College of Law					
S	Subject	Degree	S	Subject	Degree
1	Civil Law (Obligations)	Accept	6	Political systems	v. Good
2	Administrative Law	Accept	7	Arabic	Good
3	General Penal Code	Accept	8	Ruling verses	Good
4	Personal Status Law	v. Good	9	Criminal jurisprudence	Good
5	Public Finance	Good	10	Administrative Law (in English)	Accept
result			pass		

Figure 4 Certificate sheet

In the statistics sheet, we will find everything related to it, such as success and failure rates, whether for all classes or for academic subjects, in addition to the first students in the batch, and the statistics include the three attempts, as shown in figure (5).

Statistics for each subject for the second stage	Civil Law (Obligations)	Administrative Law	General Penal Code	Personal Status Law	Public Finance	Political systems	Arabic	Ruling verses	Criminal jurisprudence	Administrative Law
pass	186	198	199	200	199	199	198	197	199	191
fail	19	7	6	5	6	6	7	8	6	14
sum	205	205	205	205	205	205	205	205	205	205
%pass	91	97	97	98	97	97	97	96	97	93
%fail	9.3	3.4	2.9	2.4	2.9	2.9	3.4	3.9	2.9	6.8
sum	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
Success rate	53	58	63	73	71	72	69	68	69	62

Figure 5 Statistics sheet

In the master sheet, we will find all the details written in it as shown in the figure (6).

subject	Civil Law (Obligations)	Administrative Law	General Penal Code	Personal Status Law	Public Finance	Political systems	Arabic	Ruling verses	Criminal jurisprudence	Administrative Law	sum	ave.
	units	3	3	3	2	2	2	2	2	1		
full name	annual degree	final exam	final degree	annual degree	final exam	final degree	annual degree	final exam	final degree	annual degree	final exam	final degree
	1	Itisam Darsh Aliwi										
	Mozza											
2	Abcar Abdul Karim											
	Abdul Hussein Kazem											
3	Sincerity Qasim											
	Hashem Matar											
4	Areej Raad Aliwi Hamid											
5	Zia Murad Mirza flowart											

Figure 6 Master sheet

4. Discussions

From the previous section we note that the system is simple but accurate and contains great details, which by nature are useful to several parties in the colleges and universities and the Ministry of Higher Education, and the system is not limited, can be developed and add updates as needed, and gives accurate and quick results, and for a large number of students, Just imagine if all these statistics are calculated manually, how much time will you need? How many hands? Will the results be accurate?

5. Conclusion

From the above, we can say that the system is comprehensive for all the needs of the system of examination committee for undergraduate is accurate and fast to give results and easy to use does not require high specifications by the calculator to be applied and also does not require high skill by the user of the system and therefore recommend it before All universities to take advantage of the possibilities of the system to reduce the time and effort and get accurate results and statistics.

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